

An Instrument for the Measurement of the B-mode Polarization of the CMBR - A Design Development Proposal

It is proposed to carry out design development for a novel millimeter-wave interferometer instrument concept to study the B-mode polarization anisotropies of the Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation (CMBR).

The B-mode anisotropies, as the imprint of the inflationary gravitational waves on the CMBR, are the unequivocal signature of inflation in the early Universe. Their detection will have wide ranging fundamental impact - from theories of the early Universe to physics at the energy scales of the Grand Unified Theories (GUT) not accessible otherwise - and is tantamount to a detection of the primeval gravitational wave background.

The B-mode signal is expected to be at a very low level - about 0.1 μ Kelvin (\sim few parts in 10^8 of the 2.7 K CMBR) in the most favorable estimates. Innovative new instruments are required to reach the unprecedented levels of sensitivity and control of systematics necessary. Several instruments targeting the B-mode signal are under development or have been recently deployed. However, even with the optimistic assumption that the detection of the B-mode signal is close at hand, substantial improvements in sensitivity and immunity to systematics are needed to study its details and to allow for the models which predict significantly lower signal levels. Towards this goal, the proposal seeks to carry out design development for a novel millimeter-wave interferometer instrument targeting the CMBR-B-mode polarization signal. The development of the conceptual design has been completed. The instrument employs bolometric detectors at millimeter wavelengths and seeks to adapt interferometric techniques previously used at optical wavelengths, with additional features needed for the measurement of polarization (Stokes visibilities), and therefore has an interdisciplinary character. The primary merits of the concept are: simplicity, use of planar-only reflecting surfaces, entirely blockage free aperture, interferometer configuration and multiple modulation possibilities. These features minimize spurious instrumental polarization effects, afford reliability, stability and immunity to systematics thus allowing long integrations.

It is proposed to carry out a design study of the concept by using GRASP and ZEMAX optics design software packages. The study will result in the designs for a prototype to be built in future and a scaled down laboratory test bed. The theory needed will be developed fully and the sensitivities for ground based, balloon borne and space based versions will be calculated.

It is envisaged that this instrument can be the basis for CMBPOL, the projected Beyond Einstein Inflation Probe, recommended by the joint NSF-DOE-NASA Task Force on CMBR. It has the capability to make an initial ground based detection of the B-mode signal in advance of the CMBPOL probe in addition to help refine the strategies and final design for the space probe.

The study is a step in answering an important question of our times with wide impact - the origin and evolution of the Universe. It satisfies the broad aspirations of the scientific community at the intersection of several areas including early Universe, high energy physics and gravitational waves.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

For font size and page formatting specifications, see GPG section II.C.

	Total No. of Pages	Page No.* (Optional)*
Cover Sheet for Proposal to the National Science Foundation		
Project Summary (not to exceed 1 page)	1	_____
Table of Contents	1	_____
Project Description (Including Results from Prior NSF Support) (not to exceed 15 pages) (Exceed only if allowed by a specific program announcement/solicitation or if approved in advance by the appropriate NSF Assistant Director or designee)	15	_____
References Cited	2	_____
Biographical Sketches (Not to exceed 2 pages each)	2	_____
Budget (Plus up to 3 pages of budget justification)	4	_____
Current and Pending Support	1	_____
Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources	1	_____
Special Information/Supplementary Documentation	1	_____
Appendix (List below.) (Include only if allowed by a specific program announcement/ solicitation or if approved in advance by the appropriate NSF Assistant Director or designee)	_____	_____
Appendix Items:		

*Proposers may select any numbering mechanism for the proposal. The entire proposal however, must be paginated. Complete both columns only if the proposal is numbered consecutively.

Project Description

1. Motivation and Objectives

The detection of the B-mode (also called the tensor or the curl mode) polarization anisotropy of the CMBR, expected at less than $\sim 0.1 \mu\text{K}$ level, is the current observational challenge in experimental cosmology. The significance of its detection is well known and an excellent overview is presented in the final report of the NSF/NASA/DOE task force on cosmic microwave background research (TFCR Report, 2006), which identified *the accurate measurement of the CMBR polarization as the next critical step in extending our knowledge of both the early Universe and fundamental physics at the highest energies*. We propose a novel instrument to address this goal. A brief introduction to the field follows, by way of motivation.

The spatial pattern of the polarization of the CMBR can be decomposed into a gradient part (curl free) and a curl part (divergence free) and the two components are called the E-mode and the B-mode (in analogy with the E and B fields of the electromagnetic field). The B-mode polarization is caused by the gravitational wave background associated with inflation in the early universe. The inflationary gravitational waves result in small levels of local quadrupolar radiation anisotropies at the surface of last scattering, which, on Thomson scattering by electrons, lead to polarization. Its detection is considered to be a proof for the existence of inflation. It is also equivalent to detecting the primeval gravitational waves, whose direct detection is not expected in the near future. Inflation provides simple explanations for many important cosmological observational facts, and is thought to have occurred when the energy of the particles in the Universe was $\sim 10^{16}$ GeV, which is 10^{12} times above those attainable at particle colliders in the foreseeable future. This is also the energy scale of the Grand Unified Theories (GUT) at which the electromagnetic, weak and strong forces are believed to unify. The detection of the B-mode signal allows a measurement of the expansion rate of the universe during inflation, which is equivalent to the energy scale of inflation. This provides, for the first time, a potential observational tool for probing physics at GUT energy scales. B-mode generation is expected at two epochs – at recombination (or decoupling) and at reionization, with peaks at different angular scales. The reionization component also has implications for the primordial power spectrum, and therefore for inflationary models, and the time of the epoch of reionization (reviews for example, Hu & White 1997; Hu & Dodelson, 2002; Zaldarriaga, 2004).

The inflationary gravitational waves also introduce the curl-free E-mode polarization. However, much stronger levels of E-mode polarization, of several μK , result from the same density perturbations (scalar) which cause temperature anisotropies. These perturbations cause velocity fields leading to local quadrupolar fluctuations in the CMBR, which again by Thomson scattering result in polarization. This dominant E-mode has been detected at the expected level of a few – several μK by several groups (DASI: Kovac et al. 2002; Leitch et al. 2002, Leitch et al. 2005; CBI: Readhead et al. 2004; CAPMAP: Barkats et al. 2005; BOOMERANG: Montroy et al. 2005; WMAP: Kogut et al 2003, latest results in Page et al 2006). Gravitational lensing of this dominant E-mode results in a B-mode pattern, which corrupts the gravity wave B-mode. The expected levels of the various polarization signals are shown in Figure 1, against the multipole number along with the latest WMAP detections and limits (from Page et al 2006). The task is to map polarization patterns at less than $\sim 0.1 \mu\text{K}$ level, and to disentangle the inflationary gravity-wave induced B-mode from the E-mode, and lensing induced B-mode, often termed foregrounds (in addition to galactic dust and synchrotron radiation), by their spatial patterns. The lensing

induced B-mode foreground has its own value, which can be used to study the growth of large scale structure with implications for the neutrino mass and the dark energy equation of state. In summary, the ability to detect and map polarization at the level of the B-mode signal - $\sim 0.1 \mu\text{K}$ - has many rewards.

Figure 1 The levels of various CMBR polarization signals (adapted from Page et al 2006). Green: E-mode; Blue: expected B-mode; Red: T-E correlation; Dashed blue – B-mode due to lensing of E-mode. Dashed green and blue lines: foreground levels. The WMAP result for limit on the B-mode is shown as a blue mark at multipole moment ~ 4 , the most sensitive non-detection so far. The proposed SAPT-RShI instrument will have an expected nominal sensitivity of $\sim 0.03 \mu\text{K}$ per baseline in ~ 2 years and will be sensitive to multipoles $l < 300$ (l_{max}) corresponding to an angular scale of ~ 0.5 deg.

The B-mode signal due to scattering at recombination is modeled to be strongest at the multipole $l \sim 100$, which corresponds to an angular scale of ~ 2 deg. The component from the epoch of reionization is at larger scales of $l \sim 6$. Both have their origins in the inflationary gravitational waves. While disentangling the inflationary B-mode signal is a difficult undertaking, and is the

focus of current research (Bunn, 2003; Ponthieu, 2003; Park & Ng, 2004; Hinshaw et al. 2006), the parallel design of instruments to reach the required sensitivity is even more of a challenge. While this is an admittedly daunting task, it should not deter us from conceiving instruments that are equal to the challenge, given the importance of the eventual results. The objective of the work proposed here is to explore a novel instrument concept, with several new features well suited to measuring the CMB-B signal, limited only by the ability to disentangle it from the foregrounds (E-mode, lensing B-mode, dust and synchrotron emission etc.). *The heart of the proposed concept is the polarized rotational shear interferometer (RSI) feeding an array of bolometric detectors.* RSIs have been built at optical wavelengths without any polarization capability. We seek to adapt the technique for operation at millimeter wavelengths and incorporate features needed to measure polarization. This results in a system with characteristics expected to be critical for the success of any B-mode experiment. There are several experiments under development or deployed which attempt to detect the B-mode signal (section 3). However, instruments which incorporate widely different, “orthogonal” approaches are necessary to produce a confident detection of such a weak signal. Our concept is radically different from current instruments in its beam combination scheme where it exploits techniques from optical wavelengths. The current experiments may detect the B-mode signal at the level of ~ 0.1 μK predicted by the most favorable models – but lower tensor to scalar ratios lead to significantly smaller signals. For a value of 0.1 for this ratio r , as opposed to 0.3, the predicted B-mode signal is only ~ 0.03 μK . In addition, substantial improvements in sensitivity and immunity to systematics are necessary to study the details of the B-mode signal. With this motivation, we briefly review the instrument requirements and current instruments in the following sections and contrast them with our new instrument concept.

2. Instrument Requirements

The key features needed in a successful B-mode experiment are: (1) the least possible instrumental polarization; (2) simplicity, therefore high reliability, to allow long integrations; (3) multiple levels of differencing/modulation to combat systematics. An interferometer configuration with its inherent differencing scheme is probably critical as it suffers least from fluctuations and systematics - the DASI and CBI instruments which made the first detection of the E-mode signal (Kovac et al., 2002), the multiple peaks of the intensity power spectrum (Halverson et al., 2002) and its phase shift from the E-mode power spectrum (Readhead et al, 2004), both took advantage of interferometry. A large continuum bandwidth is needed to keep the required integration times acceptably low (few years). An excellent site is needed, a space based instrument being the best choice. For primary frequencies of operation of $\sim 90/150$ GHz, ground based instruments at sites like the South Pole or northern Chile are acceptable. Ground based instruments and balloon borne experiments can be fore-runners for future spacecrafts, allowing many different techniques to be tested with relatively short turn-around times and at much smaller costs.

3. Current Instruments

Some of the leading instruments specifically targeting the B-mode are QUAD (Church et.al., 2003), BICEP (JPL/Caltech/UCB; Keating et al., 2003), POLARBEAR, QUIET, MBI (Brown, Northwestern, Wisconsin & Cardiff; Tucker et al. 2003) , and CLOVER (UK, US; Maffei et al

2005). The QUAD instrument, now deployed at the South Pole, is a standard cassegrain configuration with a 2.6-m primary. It uses a large foam cone in front of the primary to hold the sub-reflector to avoid scattering/ blockage and loss of symmetry from a support structure. BICEP directly images the sky onto an array of polarization sensitive bolometers with a lens and uses waveguide Faraday rotators to modulate polarization. QUAD and BICEP are sister instruments targeting different multipole ranges, both using polarization sensitive bolometers. They went into operation in 2005-2006 at the South Pole (Pryke, 2006; Kovac, 2006). CLOVER is a direct imaging bolometer instrument using pseudo-correlators for measuring polarization. CLOVER is expected to go into full operation in 2009 in Chile (Taylor, 2006). The MBI is a millimeter-wave bolometric interferometer which seeks to combine the advantages of interferometry and the large bandwidths of bolometers. Current designs use small cassegrain-fed antennas as elements or flat mirrors feeding a large paraboloid which combines the signals. Beam forming networks such as Butler combiners are also being investigated. The MBI is under development and an initial version is to be fielded in 2006 (Tucker, 2006). POLARBEAR is a 3.5-m Dragone-Gregorian direct imaging bolometer instrument and uses a rotating half-wave plate for polarization modulation (Tran, 2006). QUIET is a direct imaging instrument with HEMT amplifiers (Gaier, 2003) and proposes to use the Bell Labs 7-m and is not yet funded (Winstein, 2006).

4. Drawbacks

The main drawbacks of the current designs are that they use curved surfaces and/or involve aperture blockages which introduce cross-polarization. Even Mizuguchi-Dragone telescopes still have residual off-axis cross polarization (Tran, 2003). BICEP - uses curved surfaces (lens) and measures polarization by differencing outputs from orthogonally polarized detectors (polarization sensitive bolometers, PSB), which requires exquisite gain matching. Being a direct imaging instrument, it is sensitive to effects of gain variations. CLOVER uses multiple curved reflecting surfaces. The QUAD instrument uses a cassegrain system with a blocked aperture and detector output differencing (PSB) to measure polarization. Barring MBI, all the rest are direct imaging instruments whereas interferometers have several advantages. In MBI (Tucker, 2006),- the central challenge of beam combining has not yet been handled adequately – it either uses curved surfaces for combining beams or needs a complex beam-forming network which will be lossy and difficult to implement for large number of baselines. A version of the MBI which uses horns as direct aperture elements is free of blockage and curved optics, but this configuration has to contend with the complexity of a beam forming network and its associated loss right at the input. Although all the instruments mentioned have been designed with great care to maximize sensitivity and minimize systematics, it is not clear if they are able to reach the levels required for the study of the B-mode signal in practice. Therefore, improved techniques are of great interest. Here we propose a novel instrument which combines important lessons from the above, in a radically new, yet simple configuration, simultaneously minimizing systematics and instrumental polarization. As already mentioned, the “orthogonality” of the instrument schemes can greatly improve the level of confidence in the final results.

5. The SAPT-RShI - A New Instrument Concept

5.1 Basic Features

We propose a Synthesized Aperture Polarimeter Telescope (SAPT), which employs a Rotational Shear Interferometer (RShI) feeding a bolometer array as the device to achieve beam combining.

Two realizations of the concept are depicted in figures 2 & 3, to explain the basic idea. They are essentially bolometric interferometers – therefore, like the MBI, incorporate the advantages of large bandwidths and immunity to systematics – but with a simple and elegant beam combining scheme. The primary merits of the proposed instrument concept are: (1) completely blockage free optics (2) uses only planar reflecting surfaces - these two features lead to the lowest possible instrumental polarization (3) inherently differencing interferometer configuration provides stability and immunity to systematics while directly measuring Fourier components (4) additional opportunities for modulation to control systematics exist. The RSI technique has been used at optical wavelengths for a variety of purposes – optical testing (Murty, 1964, 1966; early work), high resolution astronomical imaging through turbulent atmosphere (for example, Roddier & Roddier 1983; Kern et al 2005) and visible light tomography (Marks et al 1999). It is currently a candidate for a nulling interferometer for planet search (Ren & Serabyn 2005). Here, it is proposed to extend this technique to millimeter wavelengths for CMBR measurements, by taking advantage of large format bolometer arrays now becoming available. Polarization capability in RSIs has not been implemented so far, which we propose to incorporate by simple modifications of the optical RSI. We also note that interferometer configurations which directly measure the Fourier components of the brightness distribution may be better suited to disentangling the B-mode pattern from the E-mode pattern (for example Park & Ng, 2004), which is an important consideration.

5.2 Michelson Geometry

The instrument consists of two arms which process two copies of an aperture produced by a beam splitter. The first realization (Figure 2), in a Michelson configuration which ideally uses a non-polarizing beam splitter, readily explains the concept. This is the configuration used by the original optical RSIs. The two beams are field rotated by the two roof mirrors, and are recombined by the same beam splitter, superimposing a copy of the aperture on a rotated copy of itself. The resulting interferogram is measured by a horn coupled bolometer array. The bolometers couple to free space through the linear polarized feed horns which set their polarization response. The roof mirrors can be rotated which results in different amounts of relative field rotations. For 90 degree rotation of the roof mirrors, as shown, a relative field rotation between the arms of 180 degrees results. Therefore, each bolometer measures the interference between two diametrically opposite points on the original aperture - in other words a component of the mutual coherence of the aperture electromagnetic field. This is same as one visibility V , of the far-field brightness distribution which illuminates the aperture. Through the well known van Cittert-Zernike theorem, this is the Fourier transform of the brightness distribution, which is the basis for all aperture synthesis interferometers, widely used in radio astronomy (for example, Thompson, Swenson & Moran, 2001). The total number of visibilities measured is equal to the number of bolometers and essentially constitutes all possible non-redundant baselines for an aperture of given size and element spacing. The optics scheme is very simple and effectively functions as the beam combiner for the interferometer. Roof mirror rotations other than 90 deg allow measurement of more visibilities, with 60 deg. rotation giving robust closure phase measurements. Polarization capability is realized through the use of linear polarized horns and half-wave plates in the two arms which rotate the horn polarization to different orientations sequentially, a standard practice at many radio interferometers.

Figure 2: A simple realization of the instrument in the Michelson geometry. (a)-(c) are modulation possibilities. Rays I and II from diametrically opposite points in the input aperture arrive at the same location in the horn array. The aperture copies on the right show baseline vectors at the input pupil and how they are rotated by the two arms. Notice the 180 degree rotation between copies A & B. A 60 degree rotation forming a closure triangle is also shown. The quarter-wave plates work as half wave plates due to the two passes and are used to rotate the polarization as needed.

5.3 Mach-Zehnder Geometry

A second realization with several advantages over the first, especially with respect to polarization capability, is shown in Figure 3. This is the configuration selected for the proposed instrument. It uses a Mach-Zehnder geometry and is based on the recently implemented Quadrature Phase Interferometer (QPI: Caltech/JPL, Kern et al 2005) for optical measurements. Instead of the roof mirror, a 3-mirror configuration (a modification of the K-mirror) is employed which rotates the field by 90 degrees while simultaneously folding the propagation path by 90 degrees. The 3-mirror configuration shown is an example generated using the ZEMAX software package and is not unique. Tracing the beams through the instrument helps understand the details. The explanation here is tedious, but we do not see an alternative to gain a good understanding. Polarization states are defined by wire grids and the horns here transmit both polarizations. The first wire grid WG1, has wires arranged in a plane perpendicular to the plane of the paper, each wire being oriented parallel to the plane of paper. Therefore, it splits the input IN 1 into two orthogonal linear polarized beams, one vertical (in the plane of the paper; red \uparrow , arm I), and the other, horizontal (perpendicular to the paper; blue \odot , arm II).

Figure 3: The preferred Mach-Zehnder SAPT-RShI configuration. The two polarization paths are shown in red and blue. The aperture elements at A & a and B & b are diametrically opposite, shown by different symbols on the input pupil (bottom right). Their polarization states are decomposed as shown in colored vectorial representations. The sums of the orthogonal states from the end points of the baselines aA and bB are sensed by the horns, one sum for each horn, as shown on the horn array aperture. Diametrically opposite horns constitute baselines Aa and aA, which are also orthogonally paired in polarization, as shown by the colors (also for Bb and bB). Modulation possibilities are also indicated. More details in text.

The two beams propagate in perpendicular directions towards two 3-mirror arrangements. The 3-mirror rotators fold the paths by 90 degrees and rotate the fields by 90 degrees, also rotating the polarizations. The resulting beams are recombined by the second wire grid WG2. For the mirror arrangements shown, the rotations after recombining the beams are opposite to each other for the two arms, leading to a rotational shear of 180 degrees between them. The polarizations follow the fields and also rotate 180 degrees relative to each other. However, polarization being a spin-2 object, 180 degree rotation maintains their original orthogonal relationship. The orientations and rotations of the field and the polarization are depicted in the ray tracings shown. It is necessary to consider a vector in the input pupil and orthogonal polarization orientations to understand both the field and polarization rotations. For arm II, we pick a pupil vector parallel to the polarization and perpendicular to the plane of the paper (decided by the wire orientations in WG1) and the corresponding ZEMAX ray tracing is shown to the bottom left, in blue. For arm I, since an orthogonal linear polarization state is reflected by WG1, the same pupil vector is perpendicular to the polarization, and we need to look at the rotations for two orientations (one each for the field and the polarization), as shown in the two separate ray tracings (red). Note that the fan rays traced are oriented perpendicular to each other in arm II in the two tracings, one (top right) shows the rotation of the pupil vector (field rotation) and the second, below the first, shows the rotation of the polarization.

We also represent the aperture elements and pupil vectors in a diagram of the pupil and of the horn array as shown at the bottom right. These diagrams represent planes perpendicular to the plane of the paper and as viewed from behind the wave fronts. The pupil vector \mathbf{aA} connects diametrically opposite aperture elements shown by the symbols \times and \square . The wire grid WG1 decomposes the polarization at each of elements into two components shown in red and blue. After rotation by the mirrors, as seen from the ray traces, arm I has horizontal polarization perpendicular to the paper (\odot , red) and arm II has vertical polarization in the plane of the paper (\updownarrow , blue). As also seen in the ray tracing, copies of the pupil vector \mathbf{aA} are rotated by the two arms to be both in the plane of the paper, horizontal for arm I, and vertical for arm II. The second wire grid WG2 has wires perpendicular to the plane of the paper, and acts as a combiner. For this orientation, it directs both beams to the horn array to the right, reflecting the beam from arm I and transmitting the beam from arm II. As shown in the horn array aperture diagram (lower right), the two arms have effectively rotated the fields by 180 degrees relative to each other. The horn array propagates both polarizations, as in the QUAD instrument, for example (Murphy et. al., 2005). Effectively, each horn receives orthogonally polarized radiation from diametrically opposite points in the input aperture, and can measure the correlation between them (section 5.4), which is exactly what is needed to measure the polarization state of the input field. Therefore, each horn corresponds to a baseline in the input aperture and is sensitive to the polarized mutual coherence, also called the Stokes visibility (Hamaker, Bregman & Sault, 1996), of the input field for that baseline. The baselines are diameters of concentric circles in the aperture. The senses of rotation of the aperture elements in the two arms, which are 90 degrees in opposite directions, are shown by the red and the blue arcs outside the input pupil. A second set of pupil elements connected by pupil vector (same as baseline vector) \mathbf{bB} is also depicted. Note also that diametrically opposite horns constitute baselines rotated 180 degrees and an orthogonal combination of polarization states.

The interferometer couples the second horn array (OUT2) to the second input port (IN2) of the beam splitter WG1 where a cold absorber is shown. This port can be opened to the sky in which case an interferogram for another patch of the sky 90 degrees away can be measured. It is also

possible to place reference sources here instead, with known polarization and orientations. Some interesting possibilities which can be used to modulate the signals are readily apparent. It is possible to switch the two detector arrays between the two input ports by rotating WG2 by 90 degrees. In this orientation, the IN1 port of WG1, through arm I, is transmitted at WG2 to OUT2 and the component through arm II is reflected to OUT2. Similarly, IN2 gets coupled to OUT1. The polarization response of the system on the sky can be rotated by rotating WG1 and WG2 in synchronism with each other. For a beam combiner wire grid orientation of 45 degrees, a combination of the interferograms of the two input ports is obtained at both the horn arrays, each of which superpose diametrically opposite points and orthogonal polarization states. In summary, (1) IN1 and IN2 are coupled to OUT1 and OUT2 for orthogonal orientations of WG1 and WG2 and the coupling is switched for parallel orientation. Intermediate orientations couple a variable combination of the two input ports to the two output ports (2) A locked rotation of the two wire grids rotates the polarization response on the sky.

5.4 Complex Stokes Measurements

The bolometers measure intensities which will have a DC, on which the correlations (same as the mutual coherences or the visibilities) ride. In an adding interferometer such as the one proposed, each horn coupled detector measures a time averaged intensity $I = \langle E_{1x}^2 + E_{2y}^2 + E_{1x}E_{2y}\cos \varphi \rangle$ (see for example Rohlfs & Wilson, 2000). E_{1x} and E_{2y} are the fields due to orthogonally polarized (X & Y) and diametrically opposite aperture elements (1 & 2) and φ is the visibility phase. The DC is proportional to the sum of the intensities in the orthogonal polarization states (= total intensity integrated over the field of view of the horns) and needs to be removed. This term, $\langle E_{1x}^2 + E_{2y}^2 \rangle$, is independent of the orientation of the polarization response. This is obvious for unpolarized radiation and for polarized radiation this is still the case because we receive both polarizations. The term $\langle E_{1x}E_{2y}\cos \varphi \rangle$, however, depends on the position angle of the polarization response, if the radiation is polarized and has structure corresponding to the baseline, because it is the *correlation* between the orthogonal components. The real part of the visibility, $\Re(V) = E_{1x}E_{2y}\cos \varphi$, is in this cross product term. When cross polarized signals are cross correlated, the XY and YX correlations, obtained from diametrically opposite horns, relate to the Stokes visibilities as $-Q\sin(2\psi) + U\cos(2\psi) + j V$ and $-Q\sin(2\psi) + U\cos(2\psi) - j V$ (Thompson, Swenson & Moran 2001), where ψ is the orientation of the polarization response on the sky, Q and U represent linear polarization and V quantifies the circular component. Since V is expected to be zero for the CMBR, the XY and YX correlation both measure the same combination of Q and U, viz., $-Q\sin(2\psi) + U\cos(2\psi)$. The Stokes visibilities Q and U can be separated by a rotation of the polarization response (i.e. by changing ψ), by rotating the wire grids WG1 and WG2 in synchronism with each other. Additional measurements only at two other orientations are needed, to get Q, U and the DC. However, by rotating through a full cycle, we can also track and remove any DC changes as baselines in time. The deviations from this baseline contain the signals.

Since only the real parts of the visibilities are measured, we need an additional measurement to obtain the full complex Stokes visibilities. We use the same technique as in the previously mentioned optical Quadrature Phase Interferometer (QPI; Kern et al 2005), explained briefly below. The in-phase and quadrature components of the visibility are obtained by introducing an extra path length in one of the arms and combining measurements from horns located diametrically opposite to each other. Since the input brightness distribution is real, the visibility is Hermitian i.e. $V(u, v) = -V(-u, -v)$ and $\varphi(u, v) = -\varphi(-u, -v)$, where u and v are components of the baseline vector, V is the visibility amplitude and φ is the visibility phase. The

baselines (u, v) and $(-u, -v)$ are diametrically opposite points in the horn array. The excess path length in an arm, however, affects the phase of diametrically opposed points the same way (not Hermitian). Therefore, by introducing a phase shift of $\pi/4$, the phases become $(\phi + \pi/4)$ and $(-\phi + \pi/4)$ on the opposite horns. If we redefine the visibility phase to be $\phi_{\text{vis}} = (\phi + \pi/4)$, the measurements give ϕ_{vis} and $-(\phi_{\text{vis}} - \pi/4) + (\pi/4)$ or ϕ_{vis} and $-(\phi_{\text{vis}} - \pi/2)$, which are quadrature measurements. *Therefore, with a fixed excess path length corresponding to $(\pi/4)$ in one arm, we can make complex visibility measurements.* Combined with the rotation of the wire grids, complex Stokes visibilities Q and U can be measured. Stokes I is not measured because the XX and YY correlations are not measured. In other words, the interferometer is not sensitive to the intensity of the CMBR and only responds to polarization (in the ideal case with no cross-polarization). The DC term which is removed corresponds to the total intensity of the CMBR on the horn beam spatial scales and not on the interferometer beam scale. We note, however, that by the introduction of half-wave plates in the arms, it is possible to measure I, if desired, for the synthesized beam. Also, it is possible include a quarter-wave plate right at the input to convert the linear polarizations to circular polarizations. This option may be very expensive but if the advantages of measuring linear polarizations using circular polarized feeds turn out to be critical, the possibility exists. One of the proposed tasks (section 8) is to investigate how important is the use of circular polarization.

The full theory of the polarizing RSI has not been worked out. However, the required understanding exists as separate pieces in the literature which need to be integrated for the specific context and is one of the proposed tasks (section 8). The Mach-Zehnder realization does not easily allow measurement of visibilities for non-diametric baselines, and therefore closure measurements may not be possible. We do not think these are draw backs because, for the short baselines used here the phases should be very stable and the baselines measured constitute the full set of non-redundant baselines possible in the aperture with a close packed element configuration.

5.5 Detectors

Recently, bolometer arrays of large format have become possible, for example the 1000 element arrays for the South Pole Telescope (Ruhl et al 2004; Irwin, 2006 for a latest review). The current physical size for ~ 1000 elements is ~ 20 cm. They incorporate horn/ planar antenna coupled bolometers with Transition Edge Sensors (TES), fabricated using photo-lithographic techniques. At 100 GHz (3-mm wavelength), a 15-cm sized aperture gives a resolution scale of ~ 1 deg. The baseline length b and the corresponding multipole moment ℓ are related by $\ell \sim 2\pi b/\lambda$, therefore a 15-cm aperture would cover multipoles up to $\ell \sim 300$. This comfortably covers the peak of the B-mode power spectrum from the epoch of decoupling, at $\ell \sim 100$. In other words, recent advances in bolometer technology allow their direct use as apertures for interferometric imaging, as proposed here, with just the right size for the optimum B-mode angular scales. The expected sensitivity of these bolometers is $\sim 200\mu\text{Ks}^{1/2}$ (for ~ 30 GHz bandwidth; demonstrated at ACBAR – Arcminute Cosmology Bolometer Array Receiver, for example, Runyan et al 2003). These bolometers will be the detectors of choice for SAPT-RShI. We note that the length of integration imposed by the detector sensitivity is about the same as for BICEP/MBI/CLOVER/QUAD which use similar detectors. We note that the instrument concept is equally applicable for HEMT arrays, if they turn out to have decisive advantages, for example in terms of cryogenics requirements.

5.6 Instrument Bandwidth

Due to the fall-off of the visibility when the fringes are averaged over a wide bandwidth (the white light fringe being the extreme case of a single fringe for 100% bandwidth), we restrict the bandwidth in order to not lose sensitivity at the field edges. This is worst on the longest baselines. A 50% loss at the field edge with a 20% bandwidth (20 GHz) gives a field-of-view (FOV) of 18 synthesized beams (~ 1 deg FWHM each; 18 deg FOV; Thompson, Swenson and Moran, 2001). In a close-packed horn array, we can have 18 X 18 elements or 324 baselines or 162 simultaneous non-redundant visibility measurements. Since there are no focusing elements in the optics, a 20 deg FOV will imply a 2-3 meter sized input aperture. A 10 deg FOV will only need ~ 1 -m aperture, in our approximate calculation. This will be one of the points addressed by the proposed study (section 8). The pass band can be defined by a filter, of the multi-mesh type, for example (made by Thomas Keating/QMC/Cardiff, UK). An important avenue that we have not yet explored carefully is the possibility of using the instrument as an FTS, by modulating the length of the arms to provide a range of lags (for example, Ohta, Hattori & Matsuo 2004). The benefit to be gained would be the ability to use multi-frequency synthesis (Conway, Cornwell & Wilkinson, 1990) where the different spectral channels now provide different visibility measurements for the same physical baselines, improving the UV coverage. The bandwidth limitations would also be less severe for each of the spectral channels.

5.7 Sensitivity

While we have not made detailed sensitivity calculations, the fact that all the photons entering the aperture are used, implies from basic principles, a sensitivity same as for any other instrument of the same aperture size (see for example, Prasad and Kulkarni 1989). There may be issues related to the instantaneous angular response of the interferometer configuration used here which combines two beams at a time on each detector as opposed to combining multiple beams (Zmuidzinas, 2003). However, multiple beam combination would require beam forming networks or their equivalents (Butler combiners). Such combiners introduce input losses which affect the sensitivity, especially for large number of baselines, and are also hard to realize. One of the proposed tasks (section 8) is to calculate the sensitivity of our instrument taking into account both shot and wave noise and any effects due to the interferometer configuration. Here we make a simple estimate ignoring such effects, to give us an idea of the range of integration times that may be needed. We note that our instrument only measures $N/2$ visibilities for N aperture elements (same as horns/bolometers) unlike standard aperture synthesis radio interferometers which measure all possible $N(N-1)/2$ baselines. This, however, is not a limitation because the $N/2$ visibilities make up the set of non-redundant measurements possible for a given aperture and element spacing in a close packed configuration. In addition, the signals from the individual elements are only split into two halves, whereas for the $N(N-1)/2$ baselines $(N-1)$ -way splitting and a beam forming network are needed. In a direct detection bolometer instrument, the input losses implied will reduce the sensitivity.

A bolometer performance of $200 \mu\text{Ks}^{1/2}$ (ACBAR, Runyan et al 2003) implies a time of $\sim (200/\Delta T)^2$ seconds to reach an rms of ΔT . To detect $0.15 \mu\text{K}$, we need to reach $0.03 \mu\text{K}$. Note that the interferometer can be thought of as having a sinusoidally varying beam over the field-of-view. Therefore, the expected B-mode power on ~ 1 deg scale structures in Stokes Q and U of $0.15 \mu\text{K}$ is “beam filling” for each baseline. Accordingly, the time needed is: $(200/0.03)^2 = 1.5$ years for one baseline. While this is an approximate estimate, it is in a practical range and is

similar to what is expected for the other B-mode instruments mentioned earlier. However, to start with, we can average data to estimate the average B-mode band powers over a range of multipoles. Several baselines can also be averaged to reach required sensitivities on timescales of months, even with smaller bandwidths or poorer performance. The instrument will detect the E-mode polarization in 2 days ($0.5 \mu\text{K}$ rms, for each baseline; several baselines can again be averaged) and can determine its power spectrum, in a ~ 10 degree FOV for each observation.

5.8 Opportunities for modulation/differencing

The primary opportunity for modulation, the rotation of the wire grids, has already been discussed. As we also mentioned, it is possible to switch the signals between the bolometer arrays and to periodically make reference measurements on the second input port. It is also possible to rotate the whole instrument or the bolometer arrays. WG1 is expected to be large, and therefore is hard to rotate fast. WG2 is small, about the size of the detector array - ~ 15 cm - and therefore can be rotated fast and is expected to be the primary mechanism to overcome $1/f$ noise. One of the proposed tasks (section 8) is to understand the effects of each of these modulations to decide which ones or which combinations provide the best benefits.

5.9 Instrumental Effects

We point out that the orthogonally polarized horn-bolometer beams which form the pair of elements for each visibility measurement here are identical, not by production repeatability but because they are actually the same physical component and the same bolometer. Therefore, the gains of the detector system for the two aperture elements are identical. This greatly enhances the reliability of the polarization measurements without the need for exact gain matching required in designs which use separate horns/bolometers for orthogonal polarizations, including polarization sensitive bolometer (PSB) schemes. The reflections at the planar metal mirror surfaces of the 3-mirror rotators will cause some corruption of the polarization. This is expected to be small (see for example, Belitsky, 1998) and stable and therefore can be accurately accounted for. The angles of incidence on the three mirrors are small which should make the effect small. The mirror arrangements and the sequence of polarization rotations are symmetrical between the arms which should have a compensating effect. In addition, the wire grid used to combine the beams should reject a large fraction of the spurious polarization from the mirrors. The polarization leakage characteristics should be good, because two wire grids are used. The symmetry of the system implies compensating effects and inter-relations between leakage factors and between gain factors which can be exploited, an aspect proposed to be explored (section 8).

5.10 Summary

In summary the proposed SAPT-RShI instrument incorporates all the desirable features listed under the instrument requirements. The simple optics design is ideally suited for a space based instrument or as a balloon borne payload. The concept is particularly well suited for studying large and intermediate scale B-mode anisotropies, which are the science targets for the projected NASA Beyond Einstein Inflation Probe (CMBPOL). We note that a key recommendation of the NSF/NASA/DOE task force is “support for alternative technical approaches to detectors and instruments” (2005), in preparation for the CMBPOL with a recommended launch in 2018. While the proposed instrument concept can provide important lessons for CMBPOL, it has the potential to obtain a B-mode detection in advance of the space probe.

6. Broader Impact

Several recent scientific community reports have emphasized the importance of the B-mode polarizations studies. In particular, the 1999 National Academy of Sciences Board on Physics and Astronomy report *Gravitational Physics: Exploring the structure of Space and Time*, the 2001 report on Astronomy and Astrophysics in the New Millennium (AANM), the 2003 National Research Council report *Connecting Quarks with Cosmos (Q2C)*, the 2006 Radio, Millimeter and Sub-millimeter Planning Group (RMSPG) report to the NSF Senior Review all identified B-mode polarization measurements as a method of studying physics of the early Universe, inflation, gravitational waves, fundamental high energy and particle physics, and therefore an important priority. This underscores the broad impact the proposed study will have in satisfying a wide spread aspiration of the scientific community.

6.1 Non-CMBR and small angular scale CMBR applications

The SAPT-RShI concept has interesting applications for non-CMBR science. It can be fielded at any mm/sub-mm telescope with suitable re-imaging optics or redesigned to match a given f-ratio. Re-imaging the telescope aperture through the RSI on to the horn arrays will allow measurement of the mutual coherence at the telescope pupil. The angular response on the sky is correspondingly scaled, to tens of arcseconds for a 10-m class sub-mm antenna. The instrument should allow measurements of low level polarization and low-brightness features which need good stability and reliability, obtained here through the inherent gain matching and the interferometric differencing scheme. This has good potential for mapping of magnetic fields in star forming regions, molecular clouds and external galaxies, which are topics of current interest. We note that in this way, it will also be possible to study the small angular scale anisotropies of the CMBR polarization to the extent allowed by the curved optics (including re-imaging) and blockages of the telescope used. However, the optics of a typical telescope negates the basic strength of the concept. Nevertheless, an RSI based instrument on a telescope like the South Pole Telescope will have significant advantages for all continuum/polarization measurements. This may be a good way to probe small angular scale polarized CMBR anisotropies.

6.2 Education, Infrastructure & Society

The proposed study is preliminary and exploratory in nature and therefore is not suited to direct student involvement. However in the longer term, student education and research training are envisaged to be key components of the project (section 7). In the meantime, the PI will present a description of the study at the Radio and Geoastronomy lunch talk and at the Graduate Research Forum, both at the Center for Astrophysics (CfA), the home institution. These CfA fora are informal with sufficient opportunity for questions and discussions and are particularly well attended by students.

The GRASP software package proposed to be purchased can be used for other antenna design and analysis purposes and therefore will enhance the scientific infrastructure at the CfA. In particular it will be available for the analysis and better understanding of the polarization performance of the Submillimeter Array (SMA) antennas, a CfA facility. The unique polarization capability of the SMA has attracted a lot of interest and is being further developed currently.

A critical next step of the project would be to establish wider collaborations with groups at other institutions, in particular those with expertise in bolometer array technology. The proposed concept touches many disciplines - fundamental physics, astrophysics, optics and detector technology. Therefore, the present proposal is seen as paving the way for effective future collaboration between multiple disciplines and institutions, contributing to the national scientific infrastructure.

It is proposed to publish the results of this study in an appropriate peer reviewed journal and also present the same at an URSI conference for which travel support is requested. The URSI conferences are attended by a broad variety of engineers and scientists and have a strong interdisciplinary character. The results will also be posted at a web site linked through the Central Engineering and Radio & Geo-astronomy divisions of the CfA for broader dissemination.

The ultimate goal of the concept proposed to be studied here is to answer one of the most basic questions which has occupied our society since very early times - the origin and evolution of the Universe. This implies the broadest possible impact for the proposed study.

7. Longer term plan

It is intended to make contact with experienced CMBR groups and develop a broad collaboration of experimental, theoretical and data analysis experts encompassing multiple institutions and disciplines for the next phase of the project, with a significant student and research training component. Armed with a well studied concept and a preliminary design which would result from the current proposal, funds will be sought for design review and refinement followed by construction. In particular collaboration with groups with detector technology expertise will be sought, which is lacking at the PI's home institution. Initial contacts will be made during the course of the proposed study so that a collaboration can be in place towards the end of the proposal period, ready to launch the next phase. The current proposal will greatly enhance the chances of forging an effective collaboration. In the longer term, non-CMBR and small angular scale CMBR applications outlined earlier will be seriously pursued, again through strategic collaborations enabled by the current proposal.

8. Proposed Work, Personnel and Management

We propose the following tasks and approximate times to be spent:

1. The development of a prototype design, using ZEMAX (from Zeemax Development Corporation) for initial design & geometrical optics optimization and GRASP9 (from TICRA) for complete vector physical optics analysis, is the primary goal. Since the expected polarization signal is very weak (~ 1 part in 10^8), it is necessary to understand the instrumental polarization effects at a very low level. GRASP is widely used by the antenna/optics design community for such purpose, relevant examples being the analysis of the optics for the PLACK satellite (Franco, Fosalba & Tauber, 2003) and the QUAD instrument (Cahill et al 2004). GRASP is directly able to treat the wire grids that are used as beam splitter and beam combiner. Designs will be developed for a proto-type science instrument and a scaled down laboratory test bed. An analysis of the allowable tolerances in alignment and rotations is included. Cryogenic operation is assumed, design of cryogenics is excluded. Access to ZEMAX is available (used in the ray tracings shown)

and a 1 year license for GRASP9 will be purchased from TICRA. A LINUX system with dual 3.2 GHz CPUs is available. Allocated time: 8 weeks.

2. An investigation of the different modulation possibilities to decide optimum choices / combinations. Allocated time: 1 week.
3. Develop a full sensitivity analysis and the full theory of the polarizing RSI, as proposed here, including instrumental polarization effects. Explore possibilities of exploiting the symmetries in the system to reduce systematics and instrumental effects. The required pieces for this part exist in the literature which needs to be appropriately integrated for our context. Allocated time: 2 weeks.
4. The trade-off between bandwidth and field-of-view: what is the optimum choice? The utility of an FTS capability in this context and its feasibility. Allocated time: 1 week.
5. Does circular polarization have a critical advantage? If so, a component which may need development is an achromatic quarter-wave plate to covert orthogonal linear polarizations to cross-handed circular polarizations. A review of the current status of the technology will be carried out. The applicability of the well known Pancharatnam design method and more recent adaptations (Hariharan, 1998) will be briefly investigated with both quartz and sapphire as bi-refrangent materials. Allocated time : 0.5 week

At the end of the proposal performance period, we expect to have a well-studied concept and designs for a prototype science instrument and a laboratory test bed.

T. K. Sridharan will spend 25% of his time funded by the requested salary support and carry out all of the proposed work, according to the time-table above.

Guidance from an advisory panel consisting of Ray Blundell, Giovanni Fazio, Gary Melnick, Jim Moran, Scott Paine, Nimesh Patel, Antony Stark and Robert Wilson, all at the CfA, will be sought by periodic presentations. In this way, their combined experience and expertise will be brought to bear on the implementation of the study while making negligible demands on their time. The persons mentioned have agreed to play this role (letter of support included under supplementary documentation). Two presentations have already been made to this panel which recommended the development of this proposal.

References & Citations

- Barkats, D., Bischoff, C., Farese, P., et al. 2005, ApJ, 619, L127, “First measurements of polarization of the cosmic microwave background radiation at small angular scales from CAPMAP”
- Belitsky, V., 1998, ALMA Memo 242, “Suggestions on LSA/MMA front-end optical layout”
- Cahill, G., O’Sullivan, C., Murphy, A. et al, 2004, in Millimeter and Submillimeter Detectors for Astronomy, Proc. of the SPIE, Vol. 5498, p.396, “The quasi-optical design of the QUAD telescope”
- Bunn, E., 2003, New Astronomy Reviews, 47, 987, “Separating E from B”
- Church, S., Ade, P., Bock, J, et al 2003, New Astronomy Reviews, 47, 1083, “QUEST on DASI: a south pole CMB polarization experiment”
- Franco, G., Fosalba, P. & Tauber, J. A., 2003, A&A, 405, 349, “Systematic effects in the measurement of polarization by the PLANCK telescope”
- Gaier, T., Lawrence, C., Seiffert, M. D., et al, 2003, NewAR, 47, 1167, “Amplifier arrays for CMBR polarization”
- Hariharan, P., 1998, MeScT, 9, 1678, “Broadband super-achromatic retarders”
- Halverson, N. W., Leitch, E. M., Pryke, C., et al, 2002, ApJ, 568, 38, “Degree angular scale interferometer first results: a measurement of the cosmic microwave background angular power spectrum”
- Hamaker, J. P., Bregman, J. D., Sault, R. J., 1996, A&AS, 117, 137, “Understanding radio polarimetry. I. Mathematical foundations”
- Hinshaw, G., Nolte, M. R., Bennett, C. L., et al. 2006, astro-ph/0603451, “Three year Wilkinson Anisotropy Probe (WMAP) observations: temperature analysis”
- Hu, W., & Dodelson, S., 2002, ARA&A, 40, 171, “Cosmic microwave background anisotropies”
- Hu, W. & White, M., 1997, New Astronomy, 2, 323, “ A CMB polarization primer”
- Irwin, K., 2006, in *Fundamental Physics With Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation*, (Conference), 2006, San Diego, “Superconducting transition edge sensor bolometers and SQUID multiplexers for large format arrays of CMB detector”
- Keating, B.G., Ade, P.A.R., Bock, J.J., et al, 2003, Proc. SPIE, vol. 4843 p284, “BICEP: A large angular scale CMB polarimeter”
- Kern, B., Dimotakis, P., Martin, C., Lang, D. B., Thessin, R. N., 2005, Ap. Op., 44, 7424, “Imaging through turbulence with a quadrature phase optical interferometer”
- Kogut, A., et al. 2003, ApJS, 148, 161, “First year Wilkinson Anisotropy Probe (WMAP) observations: temperature-polarization correlation”
- Kovac, J. M., Leitch, E. M., Pryke, C., Carlstrom, J. E., Halverson, N. W., & Holzappel, W. L. 2002, Nature, 420, 772, “Detection of polarization in the cosmic microwave background using DASI”
- Kovac, J. M., 2006, in *Fundamental Physics With Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation*, (Conference), 2006, San Diego, “BICEP”
- Leitch, E. M., et al. 2002, Nature, 420, 763, “Measurement of polarization with degree angular scale interferometer”
- Maffei, B., Ade, P. A. R., Calderon, C., et al 2005 ESA Publications Series, 14, 251, “CLOVER: The CMB polarization observer”
- Montroy, T. E., Ade, P. A. R., Bock, J. J. et al. 2005, astro-ph/0507514, “A measurement of the CMB $\langle EE \rangle$ spectrum from the 2003 flight of BOOMERANG”
- Murphy, J. A., Gleeson, E., Cahill, W. et al 2005, IJIMW, 26, 505, “Millimeter-wave profiled corrugated horns for the QUAD cosmic background polarization experiment”

- Murty, M.V.R.K., 1964, JOSA, 54, 1187, “Interference between wavefronts rotated or reversed with respect to each other and its relations to spatial coherence”
- Murty, M. V. R. K., Hagerott, E. E., 1966, Ap. Op., 5, 615, “Rotational-shearing Interferometry”
- Ohta, I., Hittori, M., Matsuo, H., 2004, in *Microwave and Terahertz Photonics*, Proceedings of the SPIE, vol. 5487, Ed. Stohr, A., Jager, D. & Iezekiel, S., p1563, “Development of a super-broadband interferometer in FIR”
- Page, L., Hinshaw, G., Komatsu, E., et al, et al 2006, astro-ph/0603450, “Three year Wilkinson Anisotropy Probe (WMAP) observations: polarization analysis”
- Park, C.G., Ng, K. W., 2004, ApJ, 609, 15, “E/B separation in cosmic microwave background interferometry”
- Ponthieu, N., 2003, NewAR, 47, 1047, “First detection of polarization of the submillimeter diffuse Galactic dust emission by Archeops”
- Prasad, S. & Kulkarni, S., R., 1989, J. Opt. Soc. Am. A., 6, 1702, “Noise in optical synthesis images. I. Ideal Michelson interferometer”
- Pryke, C., 2006, in *Fundamental Physics With Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation*, (Conference), 2006, San Diego, “QUAD”
- Ren, D., Serabyn, E., 2005, Ap Opt, 44, 7070 “Symmetric nulling coronagraph using a rotational shear interferometer”
- Readhead, A. C. S., et al. 2004, Science, 306, 761, “Polarization observations with the cosmic background imager”
- Roddier, C., Roddier, F., 1983, ApJ, 270, L23, “High resolution observations of α -Orionis with a rotation shearing interferometer”
- Rohlf, K and Wilson, T. L., *Tools of Radio Astronomy*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1996.
- Runyan, M .C., Ade, P. A. R., Bhatia, R. S., et al, 2003, ApJS, 149, 265 “ACBAR: the arcminute cosmology bolometer array receiver”
- Task Force on CMBR (TFCR), Final Report, 2006, Bock et. al., astro-ph/0604101
- Taylor, A., 2006, in *Fundamental Physics With Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation*, (Conference), 2006, San Diego, “CLOVER”
- Thompson, A. R., Moran, J. M., Swenson, G. W., 2001, *Interferometry and Synthesis in Radio Astronomy*, Wiley-Interscience, New York.
- Tran, H. T., NewAR, 47, 1091 “Polarization Comparison between on-axis and off-axis dual reflector telescopes: Zemax and GRASP 8 simulations”
- Tran, H. T., 2006 in *Fundamental Physics With Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation*, (Conference), 2006, San Diego, “POLARBEAR: Ultra-high energy physics with measurement of CMB polarization”
- Tucker, G. S., Kim, J., Timbie, P. et al. 2003, NewAR, 47, 1137, “Bolometric interferometry: the millimeter-wave bolometric interferometer”
- Tucker, G., 2006 in *Fundamental Physics With Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation*, (Conference), 2006, San Diego, “Millimeter-wave bolometric interferometer”
- Winstein, B., 2006 in *Fundamental Physics With Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation*, (Conference), 2006, San Diego, “QUIET”
- Zaldarriaga, M., 2004, in *Measuring and Modeling The Universe*, Carnegie Observatories Astrophysics Series, Vol. 2, Ed. W. L. Freedman, (Cambridge: Cambridge Univ. Press), “The polarization of the cosmic microwave background”
- Zmuidzinas, J., 2003, J. Opt. Soc. Am. A, 20, 218, “Cramer-Rao sensitivity limits for astronomical instruments: implications for interferometer design”